

Designing new ultra-high temperature phase change materials from the Fe-Si-B system for thermal energy storage density above 1 MWh/m³

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ABSTRACT

New ternary Fe-Si-B alloys were developed as potential metallic phase change materials (PCMs) for application in ultra-high temperature latent heat thermal energy storage systems (LHTES). By a thermodynamic re-assessment of the Fe-Si-B system, three new Si-rich (approx. 40–50 wt%) compositions were pre-selected for further analyses. The new alloys can provide very high energy density (even above 1 MWh/m³) at melting temperatures around 1150–1200 °C. Furthermore, new PCM candidates have twice lower B content than already developed Fe-26Si-9B alloy, what is beneficial from the economic point of view. For the sake of experimental validation, the PCM candidates were produced by the arc melting technique. The outputs of thermodynamic calculations were verified in detailed microstructural studies and differential scanning calorimetry experiments. In the case of the newly developed Fe-46Si-5B and already designed Fe-26Si-9B alloy, the energy density higher than 1 MWh/m³ was experimentally confirmed.

1. Introduction

Latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) has been widely accepted as distributed and site-independent energy storage solution for both domestic and industrial applications [1]. Nowadays, this technology is mostly considered as a support of concentrated solar power (CSP) systems, giving a desired backup in sunless periods or in steam or coal-fired ultra-supercritical power plants. The overall performance of each LHTES system is driven by thermophysical properties of an applied phase change material (PCM). Among various organic and inorganic substances, high temperature metallic PCMs provide several benefits, namely a high specific enthalpy of fusion at high operational temperatures, a high thermal conductivity, a low volumetric expansion, and good durability.

So far, the most common metallic alloys considered as PCMs are those based on Al or Al-Si based near eutectic alloys. In this regard, it is worth to mention contribution of the research group led by Professor Takahiro Nomura [2–5]. Beside of using conventional as-cast Al-based alloys, the authors have also developed a microencapsulation technique [6,7] of aluminum based PCMs that brings new opportunities for safe and efficient long-term LHTES operations (up to 3000 cycles) [8].

Nevertheless, the main application of Al-based PCMs is focused on the Carnot battery and the reuse of a conventional ultra-supercritical power plants with a maximum operating temperature of approximately 650 °C [9]. Furthermore, the Al-based PCMs show latent heat in the range of 250–400 J/g, and by taking their relatively low specific weight, a total stored energy capacity is not higher than 0.3 MWh/m³.

Why do we need ultra-high temperature materials (i.e. these operating at temperatures beyond 1000 °C, as it is defined by Zhou et al. [10])?

Potential receivers of such materials are recently developed cost-effective latent heat thermophotovoltaic (LHTPV) batteries that are a kind of power-to-heat-to-power storage systems that store electricity in the form of latent heat at very high temperatures (>1,000 °C) and converts it back to electricity on demand, using thermophotovoltaics [11]. As this technology is mostly dedicated for space industry applications [12], it is very important to ensure that a PCM introduced to LHTPV batteries combines: melting point above 1000 °C; and a high latent heat and high density to ensure a storage capacity of >1 MWh/m³ (so, compared to that of pressurized hydrogen).

Regarding ultra-high temperature applications Cu and its alloys are also considered as potential PCM because of its high melting point (T_{mCu}

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= 1083 °C), high thermal conductivity. In recent times, Cu-based PCMs have been studied extensively, mostly in their macro-encapsulated form. The reported examples include works by Akiyama et al. [13], on encapsulation of pure Cu or Sugo et al. [14] on Cu–Fe miscibility gap alloys produced by a powder metallurgy process. Although, the preliminary results seems to be promising, unfortunately latent heat of Cu is only 208.7 kJ/kg (or 0.52 MWh/m³), thus Cu does not fulfil the requirement of high stored energy density.

Recently, we have proposed to use the Fe-26Si-9B (wt %) ternary eutectic alloy as a new metallic PCM combining excellent functional properties in terms of application in highly efficient LHTES systems combined with thermophotovoltaic or thermionic energy converters that typically operate at temperatures above 1000 °C [15–17]. It was reported that this eutectic alloy exhibits a high thermal conductivity (10–30 W/mK) and a theoretical energy density above >1 MWh/m³ for a melting temperature of 1150 °C [18]. This involves 10 times less volume of storing container than current molten salt-based TES, only comparable to pressurized H₂ storage and provides a great potential to exceed the energy density of most current electrochemical storage technologies [17]. The alloy was designed based on the concept of combining silicon and boron that possess the highest heat of fusion among all metallic and non-metallic elements ($\Delta H = 1800$ J/g and $\Delta H = 4640$ J/g, respectively [19,20]). However, applicability of pure Si and eutectic Si-B alloys is quite strongly limited by (i) their high volumetric expansions during the phase change (around 10 % [21]) and by (ii) significantly high reactivity with most of existed refractories [22,23]. Thus, upon designing the Fe-26Si-9B alloy, the main role of iron addition was to reduce these adverse effects taking place during solid ↔ liquid phase changes [24]. Currently, we are working on a large-scale fabrication of this material by utilizing a special thermochemical treatment of B-rich ores, ferrosilicons and ferroborens as raw materials. During technological trials at a metallurgical plant, we were able to produce around 700 kg of the alloy (the results have not been published yet as they are subjected to patent protection, while a relevant paper is now under review). The process that we have developed might be easily adopted for a large-scale production of other Fe-Si-B alloys.

In this work, we make a thermodynamical re-assessment of the Fe-Si-B system to find out, if there are any other ternary near eutectic or/and congruently melting compositions having even higher heat of fusion. We have assumed that increasing Si content should enhance the heat of fusion of the Fe-Si-B alloys. Furthermore, by considering economical aspects of the usage of Fe-Si-B alloys as PCMs, and by taking into account very high price and geographically limited availability of boron [25,26], the other justification for re-designing the Fe-26Si-9B alloy is to reduce the boron content. Thus, the research question put in this work is as follows: “Can we re-arrange a chemical composition of the Fe-26Si-9B alloy in order to enhance its heat of fusion and at the same time, to move towards increased content of more abundant elements?”.

To provide answer to this question, the thermodynamic calculations were followed up with a lab-scale fabrication of alloys and experimental validation of their thermodynamic properties. Finally, the main novelty of this work is based on a re-designing of Fe-Si-B alloys towards more sustainable compositions that offer the energy storage density above 1 MWh/m³ at ultra-high temperatures.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Thermodynamic assessment

The Phase Diagram module of FactSage 8.1 software powered by the FTLite database, was used to calculate the ternary Fe-Si-B diagram. The liquidus projection was calculated to extract chemical compositions of Fe-Si-B alloys having in-variant points with the liquid phase (so, being formed either in eutectic or peritectic reactions). For these alloys, the Equilib module was used to predict the evolution of enthalpy over temperature range of 20–1800 °C for assumed mass of 100 g of each

alloy, and to further evaluate the heat of fusion (ΔH_f), temperature range of the phase transformation (ΔT) and density. For the sake of conversion from of heat of fusion units from J/g to MWh/m³, a FactSage calculated density at liquidus temperature of each alloy was used. It should be mentioned that, as density at liquidus is for all alloys lower than that at room temperature, this is the “worst case scenario”, while all the predicted values are rather underestimated.

2.2. Experimental works

Small samples (mass of ~ 1 g) of the Fe-Si-B alloys having compositions predicted by the FactSage calculations were produced by electric arc melting (Buehler MAM-1, Germany) of properly weighted mixtures of pure elements (99.99 % Fe, ThermoFisher; solar grade Si, Sintef Industry; 99.97 % B, Shanghai Aladdin Biochemical Technology Co Ltd, China). The melting process was carried out under non-oxidizing conditions by using an initial high vacuum of 10⁻⁵ mbar, multiple purging the chamber with high purity Ar (99.999 %) and pre-melting of Zr oxygen getter. A consumable tungsten electrode was used to produce electric arc having a temperature around 3500 °C, as declared by the producer of the furnace (the real temperature of the arc was not measured). Each alloy piece was remelted 4 times to ensure a better structure and chemical composition homogeneity. Chemical compositions of the arc-melted alloys were experimentally examined by ICP-SFMS method according to SS-EN ISO 17294-2:2023, US EPA Method 200.8:1994 (ALS Scandinavia AB Luleå, Sweden). The microscopic analyses of arc-melted samples were made on mechanically polished cross-sections of alloy pieces. Finally, microstructural features of the alloys were revealed by inspections with a scanning electron microscope (FEI Scios, USA) equipped with X-Ray energy dispersive spectroscopy detector and electron backscatter diffraction system (SEM/EDS/EBSD). For each sample, several EBSD scans were performed using various step-sizes (0.2–2 µm) to collect around 30 000 measurement points in each scan. The TSL OIM Analysis 5 software uses *Confidence Index* > 0.1 as the threshold value, for which the point is basically classified as correctly indexed. The heat of fusion of the Fe-Si-B alloys was measured by differential scanning calorimetry technique (DSC, Netzsch STA 449 F3 Jupiter, Germany) and quantified by a dedicated software (Netzsch Proteus Thermal Analysis 6.1.0). For each alloy a DSC scan was performed within a temperature range of 20–1400 °C, by using heating/cooling rates of 10 °C·min⁻¹, and under flowing argon atmosphere. To protect the alloys against undesired interaction, commercial alumina containers were spray-coated with a boron nitride slurry (as it was previously documented that this ceramic material shows exceptional inertness towards Si-based melts [27]).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Calphad-based alloys design, heat of fusion and melting behavior

The Fe-Si-B alloys compositions having three-point intersections with a liquid phase are marked in isothermal projections of the FactSage calculated ternary diagram (Fig. 1a and b) and further listed in Table 1.

The software predicted 12 different ternary compositions. For the sake of comparison, the already developed Fe-26Si-9B alloy (Alloy#8, Table 1) was taken as the reference material. It should be noted that the presently used FactSage version predicts slightly different composition of this alloy (Fe-24Si-11B), however in order to avoid misunderstanding, we decided to keep and use the previous notation throughout the manuscript. The results of calculations on the enthalpy evolution as a function of temperature for Si-based alloys, as well as Fe- and B-rich ones, are given in Fig. 1c and d, respectively. It is observed that for all chosen Si-rich alloys (Fig. 1c), an additional enthalpy step increase is observed due to a solid-state reaction taking place around 950–1050 °C (depending on the alloy's chemistry). Based on the results of phase equilibria calculations, this step was associated with a phase

Fig. 1. The results of FactSage calculations: isothermal projection of the Fe-Si-B system with marked new alloys' compositions (a); enlarged area of Fe-Si-B system showing Si-rich and Fe-rich compositions (b). Total enthalpy evolution for Si-rich (c), Fe-rich and B-rich alloys (d).

Table 1

The results of FactSage calculations: Chemical compositions, liquidus temperatures, heat of fusion and predicted phase composition of ternary Fe-Si-B alloys having three-point intersections with a liquid phase.

Alloy #	Chemical composition [% mass]	Liquidus T [°C]	Density at Liquidus [g/cm ³]	Melting Temperature range (ΔT) [°C]	Heat of fusion (ΔH _f) [MWh/m ³]	Phases in equilibrium with a liquid					
Type	Fe	B	Si								
1	B-rich	69	23.1	8	1583	4.3849	279.6	1.62	SiBn	Si	Rhombohedral-boron(beta)
2	B-rich	72.2	20.8	6.9	1442	4.6085	291.8	1.77	FeB	SiBn	Si
3	Si-rich	35.8	4.6	59.7	1272	3.3496	103	1.29	Si(B)	Si	SiB ₃
4	Fe-rich	96	3.7	0.3	1179	6.7242	2.3	0.57	BCC solid solution	Fe ₂ B	FCC solid solution
5	Si-rich	46	4.4	49.6	1168	3.6953	19	1.12	Si	FeSi ₂	SiB ₃
6	Fe-rich	86.9	3.2	10	1161	5.865	24	0.64	FeB	Fe ₃ Si	Fe ₂ B
7	Si-rich	49	5	45.9	1159	3.799	10	1.09	SiB ₆	FeSi ₂	SiB ₃
8 (ref)	Fe-rich	65.1	10.8	24	1150	4.4223	0	1.09	FeB	SiB ₆	FeSi
9	Si-rich	51.1	5.3	43.5	1149	3.8758	0	1.07	SiB ₆	FeSi ₂	FeSi
10	Fe-rich	80	2.3	17.7	1147	5.3599	51	0.62	FeB	Fe ₂ Si	FeSi
11	Fe-rich	85.1	3.2	11.7	1137	5.7333	0.7	0.63	FeB	Fe ₃ Si	Fe ₂ B
12	Fe-rich	83	2.5	14.5	1131	5.5832	1	0.58	FeB	Fe ₃ Si	Fe ₂ Si

transformation between various iron silicides ($\text{FeSi}_2 \leftrightarrow \text{Fe}_3\text{Si}_7$). It should be also noted that except the Alloys #8 and #9, the other Si-rich alloys undergo solid \leftrightarrow liquid phase change in some certain temperature range (ΔT). This transformation range in most of the cases is rather narrow ($\Delta T = 0, 10, 19^\circ\text{C}$), except the Alloy#3 for which is around 103°C .

By comparing the results of thermodynamic calculations in terms of the total enthalpy of fusion and melting temperature range it is found that:

- 1) The Fe-Si-B alloys highly alloyed with boron (namely, Alloys #1 and #2) exhibit high ΔH_f values. On the other hand, the phase change takes place over a very wide temperature range ($\Delta T = 280\text{--}290^\circ\text{C}$), what is not acceptable from the point of view of the LHTES application [28].
- 2) The Fe-rich alloys (Alloys #4; #6; #10, #11; #12) show rather low heat of fusion, and in terms of energy density, the values are not higher than $\Delta H_f = 0.57\text{--}0.64 \text{ MWh/m}^3$.
- 3) As expected, the Si-rich alloys (Alloys #3; #5; #7, #9) show almost twice the higher enthalpy of fusion than that of Fe-rich counterparts.

For all Si-rich alloys ΔH values higher than 1 MWh/m^3 were predicted for a liquidus temperatures around $1150\text{--}1170^\circ\text{C}$.

- 4) Most of the Si-rich alloys melt over certain temperature range, so they combine both latent and sensible heat. However, except the Alloy #3 ($\Delta T = 103^\circ\text{C}$), the other materials undergo a full solid \leftrightarrow liquid change in a relatively low ΔT (between 0 up to 19°C).

The basic thermodynamic properties received from the FactSage indicate that all Si-rich PCM candidates show at least comparable ΔH to that of the reference Fe-24Si-9B alloy (Alloy#8). Therefore, it seems that increased Si content in the new alloys provide the same energy density, despite half the B content (4–5.3 vs. 9 wt%) as compared to the previously developed material.

Finally, we narrowed our focus to Si-rich alloys (#3, #5, #7, #9 in Table 1) because of their high calculated enthalpy of fusion ($\sim 1.1\text{--}1.3 \text{ MWh/m}^3$) and relatively low melting ranges. In contrast, B-rich alloys were predicted to melt over an unacceptably wide temperature span ($\sim 280\text{--}290^\circ\text{C}$) despite high enthalpy, and Fe-rich alloys had much lower enthalpy ($< 0.65 \text{ MWh/m}^3$). This rationale is sound and in line

Fig. 2. A macroscopic view (a) and respective SEM images (a-e) of arc-melted Fe-Si-B alloys. Phase constituents were identified by using local EBSD and EDS microanalyses.

with expectations: adding Si boosts latent heat, while excessive B or Fe dilutes it or broadens the phase change interval. The calculated values (e.g. ~ 1.1 MWh/m³ for alloys around 45–50 % Si) are plausible, and indeed similar magnitudes were reported in prior modeling of the eutectic Fe-26Si-9B (~ 0.87 – 0.95 MWh/m³ predicted).

3.2. Microstructural characterization

The macroscopic image of arc-melted alloys is shown in Fig. 2a. It should be noted that a rounded shape of arc-melted alloy pieces (Fig. 2a) suggests a rather low volumetric expansion during solidification (as opposite to arc-melted pure Si and Si-B alloys [27]). Microstructural features of the alloys are revealed in Fig. 2b–e. Generally, the identified phase compositions show a good agreement with these predicted by the results of thermodynamic calculations. The alloys' microstructure consisted of a matrix of Fe-Si secondary solid solutions; and Si or various iron silicides precipitates accompanied by a primary crystals of silicon borides. The only one exception was previously reported microstructure of the Alloy #8 (Fig. 2d) that also include iron boride phase (FeB + FeSi + SiB₆) [29]. Nevertheless, some discrepancies between predicted and experimentally confirmed phases were found for Si-borides (having the SEM revealed morphology of dark regular particles).

Although the FactSage results pointed towards a stability of SiB₃ or SiB₆ phases (Table 1), the best fitting of EBSD data (reflected by the highest Confidence Index values) was obtained for a hexagonal SiB_n boride (when the n was equal to 36).

A boron-rich part of the binary Si-B phase diagram has been discussed for a long time, while few contradicted findings have been presented over the years [30]. The most recent form of this diagram presented by Olesinski and Abbaschian [31] assumes a presence of SiB₃ (the metastable one); SiB₆ and SiB_n (the one having the highest melting point) phases in a narrow Si dissolubility range closed to that of rhombohedral boron. In the present case, we should assume that rapid quenching conditions imposed in the arc-melting method facilitate a non-equilibrium solidification path. This finding is supported by the results of previous works [32] documenting a co-existence of various boron-rich Si-B intermetallics in rapidly quenched binary alloys. Exemplary results of the SEM/EDS/EBSD analyses are given in Fig. 3.

3.3. Heat of fusion – DSC results

The results of FactSage calculations were verified in the DSC experiments on Fe-Si-B alloys produced by the arc-melting technique (Figs. 4 and 5) (Table 2). By using a peak area observed on DSC heat flow vs. T diagrams, the experimental ΔH was extracted and then compared to that established in the thermodynamic simulations. Before starting the experiments on Fe-Si-B alloys, we used a high purity Si (solar grade) to validate the DSC setup. The presently used DSC procedure and settings were adopted from previously reported paper on measurements of temperature and heat of phase transformation of pure silicon [33]. In the present work, quantification of the DSC run for the pure Si (Fig. 4) proved the feasibility of applied experimental conditions. The received

Fig. 3. Exemplary results of the SEM/EDS/EBSD analyses obtained for the Alloy #5 (a); Alloy#7 (b); Alloy #8 (c); Alloy #9 (d): the EBSD phase maps and EDS mapping.

Fig. 4. A DSC curve recorded for pure Si (a reference material).

ΔH_f of 1711 J/g was only 5 % lower than the theoretical value of 1800 J/g [34], while the peak recorded during the continuous heating at $10^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ was observed at $T = 1411\text{--}1428^{\circ}\text{C}$ (the theoretical melting point of Si is $T_m = 1414^{\circ}\text{C}$). Thus, these rather small discrepancies may suggest that the DSC experiments were properly designed. A difference between T_{onset} and T_{end} of a DSC peak was used to evaluate melting temperature range (ΔT) of the alloys at least comparatively under applied experimental conditions. However, it should be noted that due to applied continuous heating the obtained values are overestimated in some extent, what is clearly confirmed by the $\Delta T = 17^{\circ}\text{C}$ for pure Si.

The following findings are drawn from the DSC results obtained for the Fe-Si-B alloys (Fig. 5):

- 1) During a continuous heating at $10^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ the new Fe-Si-B alloys melt in a rather low temperature range (ΔT between $23\text{--}68^{\circ}\text{C}$).
- 2) There are some discrepancies between ΔH_f values predicted by the FactStage approach and these measured by the DSC technique.

Among all investigated materials, the ΔH_f value above $1\text{ MWh}/\text{m}^3$ value was experimentally confirmed for the Fe-26Si-9B (Alloy #8) and Fe-46Si-5B (Alloy #7) alloys. Indeed, for both alloys, a very good agreement between predicted and experimentally measured heat of fusion

Fig. 5. DSC curves recorded for newly developed Fe-Si-B alloys: Fe-49Si-4B (alloy #5) (a); Fe-46Si-5B (alloy #7) (b); Fe-26Si-9B (alloy #8) (c); Fe-43Si-5B (d).

Table 2

Comparison of FactSage and DSC results on Heat of fusion and melting temperatures of selected Fe-Si-B alloys.

Chemical composition, ICP-MS [wt%]			Chemical composition, ICP-MS [wt%]			Melting Temperature range (ΔT) [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]			Heat of fusion (ΔH_f) [J/g]		Heat of fusion (ΔH_f) [MWh/ m^3]			
Alloy no.	Fe	B	Si	Fe	B	Si	FactSage	DSC T_{onset}	DSC T_{max}	DSC T_{end}	FactSage	DSC	FactSage	DSC
Pure Si	–	–	99.999	–	–	–	1414 (0)	1411	1427	1428	1788	1711	1.27	1.22 (4.0%)*
5	46.000	4.447	49.553	45.472	4.243	50.285	1149–1167 (18)	1172	1199	1203	1090	580	1.12	0.623 (44.4%)*
7	49.032	5.034	45.934	47.968	4.666	47.366	1149–1159 (10)	1173	1190	1196	1037	960	1.09	1.064 (2.4%)*
8	65.104	10.848	24.048	65.120	8.973	25.908	1150 (0)	1196	1242	1264	888	834	1.09	1.02 (6.4%)*
9	51.124	5.349	43.527	50.998	4.855	44.146	1149 (0)	1174	1191	1201	997	688	1.07	0.879 (17.9%)* ₁

*a difference between predicted vs. DSC established values.

fusion was obtained. To our best knowledge, this is so far the highest experimentally documented energy density for metallic PCM alloy at temperature range of 1100–1300 °C. In this regard, this result places the alloy beyond the already existed capabilities of PCMs reported in the literature (Fig. 6) [35]. As it has been shown by Datas et al. [36], the energy density of ~ 1 MWh/m³ is 2–6 times higher than that of Li-ion batteries, 10–20 times higher than that of lead-acid batteries and 5–10 times than that of the current state of the art molten salt-based TES systems utilized in CSP applications. The underperformance of Alloy #5 and #9 might be due to their solidification paths: for instance, FactSage predicted Alloy #5 would melt in a narrow $\Delta T \sim 19$ °C with phases Si + FeSi + SiB. If in reality an additional phase or segregation occurs (e.g. primary Si crystals or a ternary compound formation), part of the silicon may melt at a higher temperature, leaving a smaller latent heat peak around the main eutectic. From the FactSage calculation it is noted that all Si-rich alloys show a solid-state phase transition near 850–1050 °C. This pre-melting reaction would consume a bit of energy (sensible/latent), but it is relatively minor. A more impactful factor could be the presence of the newly identified FeSiB ternary phase. If FeSiB (or a similar ternary borosilicide) forms in the Si-rich alloys, it might not be included in the FTLite database used for FactSage calculations. Omission of such a phase in the model could lead to an overestimation of latent heat – because the simulation might assume more Si segregates as pure Si or SiB (melting at lower temperature with high ΔH), whereas experimentally some Si is tied up in FeSiB which melts differently. Unfortunately, as neither FactSage nor EBSD databases include ternary FeSiB intermetallics, it is not possible to experimentally confirm existence of such phases. In summary, the thermodynamic calculations are a strong guide, but they might not cover all possible solutions.

Nevertheless, in order to make a deeper insight into a possible impact of ternary Fe-Si-B intermetallics on latent heat of fusion of examined alloys, we reviewed reported literature data on the Fe-Si-B system. Specifically, we took into account ternary Fe-Si-B phases predicted in CALPHAD calculation by Poletti and Battezzati [37] and by Zaitsev et al. [38], as well as the results previously published by our team [29] (given in Table 3). By using predicted compositions of ternary phases we made another round of the FactSage calculations. It is clearly observed that ternary Fe-Si-B compounds show rather low specific ΔH_f as compared to pure silicon (1800 J/g) [34] and binary eutectic Fe-Si alloys (930–1010 J/g) [39,40], so their possible presence should negatively affect a heat of fusion of Fe-Si-B alloys. However, a precise and more certain identification of both ternary phases and silicon borides, would require using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) based diffraction tools such as

Fig. 6. A possible energy storage capacity vs. melting temperature of PCMs: a comparison of presently obtained results with these reported in the literature (based on [17;35]).

Table 3

The results of FactSage calculations on thermophysical properties of ternary Fe-Si-B intermetallics reported in the literature.

Phase formula	Chemical composition (at. %)			Solidus T [°C]	Liquidus T [°C]	Heat of fusion [J/g]
	Fe	Si	B			
Fe _{4.7} Si ₂ B [23]	61.04	25.97	12.99	1130	1187	547.11
Fe ₂ Si _{0.4} B _{0.6} [23]	66.67	13.33	20.00	1156	1233	517.13
Fe ₅ Si ₁ B ₂ [23]	62.50	12.50	25.00	1156	1339	683.65
Fe ₆ SiB [24]	75.00	12.50	12.50	1179	1221	373.5
FeSiB ₃ [15]	20.00	20.00	60.00	994	1147	820.98

nanobeam precession TEM or atomic resolution STEM HAADF.

The goal for a PCM is often a sharp phase change, but the new alloys do exhibit some melting ranges under DSC heating (ΔT of 23–68 °C for a 10 K/min ramp). The continuous heating tends to overestimate the apparent melting range (e.g. pure Si showed $\Delta T \approx 17$ °C instead of 0 °C). When extrapolated to equilibrium, most of the proposed alloys likely have invariant or near-invariant behavior (predicted $\Delta T \leq 20$ °C). Notably, Alloy #7 (Fe-46Si-5B) melted over ~ 23 °C in DSC, which is still quite narrow in practical terms. Alloy #8 (Fe-26Si-9B) showed a larger $\Delta T \approx 68$ °C in the DSC run, reflecting its off-eutectic composition. We believe that only Fe-46Si-5B and Fe-26Si-9B truly meet the “narrow $\Delta T +$ high ΔH ” criterion among the tested alloys. This conclusion is supported by the fact that Alloy #9 and Alloy #5, despite high Si, did not fully deliver on the desired properties. A critical reader might wonder if further optimization (e.g. slight tweaks in Si/B ratio or using slower cooling to get closer to equilibrium microstructure) could improve those alloys. It could be also consider whether Alloy #9 predicted congruent melting at 1149 °C was adversely affected by boron loss (thus no longer congruent). Overall, the thermodynamic foundation is solid, and the experimental results mostly reinforce it, with the exception of the two alloys where the model over-predicted latent heat. This does not invalidate the approach, but it suggests that Fe-46Si-5B is the standout composition, while others might need further investigation or refinement.

To summarize this part, it is worth underlining that the latent heat of Fe-Si-B alloys seems to be strongly affected by their phase compositions. From our theoretical and experimental studies supported by literature data, it appears that enhancement of ΔH_f can be obtained by increasing content of Si, that in turn leads to a higher fraction of Si and silicide based phases at the expense of low ΔH_f borides and silicoborides.

4. Conclusions and future remarks

In this work, the results of thermodynamic re-assessment of the Fe-Si-B system were carried out, in terms of designing new PCMs for high temperature applications. Consequently, three new Si-rich alloys were proposed as potential candidates and then theoretically and experimentally compared to the already developed Fe-26Si-9B alloy. According to thermodynamic predictions, all the alloys should provide the high heat of fusion $\Delta H > 1$ MWh/m³ in a narrow temperature range (ΔT up to 20 °C). However, the results of DSC studies confirmed these findings only for the Fe-26Si-9B reference and newly developed Fe-46Si-5B alloy. It is also worth mentioning that the new alloy has almost half the B content as compared to the Fe-26Si-9B counterpart, what is beneficial from the economic point of view.

Although, this high storing energy density was experimentally confirmed for the first time for a metallic PCM and provided a very promising first indication for future development, there are still several functional and technical properties that ought to be evaluated before the final application in TES systems. Specifically, the other thermophysical

properties including thermal conductivity, volumetric expansion and enthalpy evolution over cyclic phase changes, must be examined in detail. Furthermore, the thermochemical compatibility of the new alloy (s) with refractories and a lack of properties degradation during long-term service is a particularly important practical aspect that must be included in the future research actions.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Wojciech Polkowski: Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Paolo Lai Zhong Lo Biundo:** . **Jianmeng Jiao:** Methodology, Investigation. **Maria Wallin:** Project administration, Data curation. **Adelajda Polkowska:** Methodology, Investigation. **Filip Kateusz:** Methodology, Investigation. **Merete Tangstad:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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